

POSTBUCKLING FAILURE OF PLATES WITH HOLES

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses a study which focused on understanding the mechanisms associated with failure of plates with centrally located circular holes and which were loaded considerably into the postbuckling range of deflections. The study was numerical and experimental in nature and had as a goal the prediction of failure using existing failure data and a stress analysis. The maximum stress failure criterion was used to predict both intra- and interlaminar failure. Four laminates were studied and the phenomenon of mode jumping, or the sudden changing from one postbuckled configuration to another, is addressed. The study concludes that failure of the $(\pm 45/0/90)_{2S}$ and $(\pm 45/0_2)_{2S}$ laminates, which occurs at about 6 times the buckling load, is predictable and is due to fiber-direction compression failure. Failure of the $(\pm 45/0_6)_S$ laminate is due to interlaminar shear and failure of the $(\pm 45)_4S$ is dominated by material nonlinearities.

1. INTRODUCTION

The ability to accurately predict failure of composite plates loaded in the postbuckling range of deflections is a key step in the quest to find the most efficient use of materials. If limiting the load to buckling levels is inefficient, then how far into the postbuckling range can a plate be loaded? Hopefully, three, four, or five times the buckling load can be achieved. Clearly, the exact level has to be established during the design of the particular structure that depends on postbuckling strength. To mature to the point that using composite structures in the postbuckling range is routine will require considerably more understanding than presently exists in the area, particularly if designers not versed in the complicated topics of nonlinear structural mechanics are to successfully do their job.

The study discussed here had as a goal the evaluation of the ability to a priori predict failure of flat plates with centrally located circular holes loaded far beyond the buckling load. Existing material failure data from previous studies were used. To predict failure, it is necessary to: (1) accurately predict stresses in the plate for a range of loads; (2) define failure; and, (3) determine the location and the mode of failure. Of particular importance is the prediction of interlaminar stresses. Postbuckling response may include a sudden change of configuration, particularly to a configuration with multiple halfwaves in the loading direction. With multiple halfwaves, interlaminar shear failure along nodal

lines is a possibility [1]. One phase of the present study addressed the prediction of postbuckling plate response, including failure. In another phase of the study experiments were designed and conducted. The postbuckling response of plates was observed and measured, and failure information gathered. The plate failure data were compared with the predictions. The sections to follow briefly describe both phases of the work.

2. PROBLEM STUDIED

The specific problem studied is shown in fig. 1. Nomenclature, analysis coordinate system, dimensions, and instrumentation used in the experiments are shown. The plates considered were clamped along the top and bottom edges, which were loaded, and simply supported along the adjacent side edges. The loading consisted of moving the top edge downward a known amount, u , the bottom edge not moving. The downward displacement of the top edge was uniform across the plate width. There were no restraints on the tangential or normal displacements along the side edges. A feature that was important to consider was the fact that the actual dimensions of the plate were larger than the region within the supports. To clamp the top and bottom edges, these edges had to extend into the clamps. To be simply supported along the sides, a narrow portion of the plate had to extend outside the line of simple supports. These features were included in the model and are indicated in the figure, the dotted lines showing the lines along which the clamped and simply supported conditions were enforced. All plates considered had a 76 mm diameter hole. Between the supports the plates were 254 mm square. Overall, the plates were 279 mm square. Considering the plate width to be the 254 mm, the hole diameter to plate width ratio was 0.3.

Instrumentation included strain gages, labeled 'sg.' in the figure, and displacement transducers, labeled 'LVDT.' Shadow moire measurements of the out-of-plane displacements were made. Displacement transducers measured the downward displacement of the top edge and the out-of-plane deflection at the edge of the hole. Back-to-back gages measured strains at selected locations. Four graphite-epoxy plates, with layups of $(\pm 45/0/90)_2S$, $(\pm 45/0_2)_2S$, $(\pm 45/0_6)_S$, and $(\pm 45)_4S$, were considered. The plate material was AS4/3502. The plates were nominally 2.16 mm thick. Because the anisotropic coefficients [2] for these laminates were small, a quarter-plate analysis could be used in the modeling.

3. PREDICTION OF RESPONSE

The prediction of plate response into the postbuckling range and for the conditions depicted in fig. 1 was done using the finite-element approach. Owing to the complex nature of the boundary conditions of the actual plate, i.e., the extensions, no other approach was considered. The finite-element analysis used a shear deformable approach, not because the plates were thick, but because a shear deformable theory is easier to formulate than a Kirchhoff-type theory. A geometrically nonlinear analysis, using linear elastic properties, was used. The deformations and intralaminar stresses were computed directly from the finite-element analysis. The interlaminar stresses were obtained by integrating the equations of elasticity through the thickness of the laminate. The work of Chaudhuri and Seide [3] provided guidance in this phase of the work, and considerable checking of the method relative to closed-form solutions of simpler problems [4] was done to gain confidence that the interlaminar stress computations were accurate. The issue of multiple halfwaves in the loading direction was addressed in an approximate fashion. Specifically, instead of directly addressing the issue of configuration changes during the loading process, which is what could actually occur, the plate response with one halfwave in the loading direction and with two half waves in the loading direction were studied separately by using initial imperfections to force the plate into one configuration or the other. In each case, one halfwave perpendicular to the loading direction was assumed. The issue of configuration change during the loading process, an extremely important issue, was considered beyond the scope of the

study.

As part of the analysis, buckling loads were predicted with a separate finite element program. Though buckling loads per se were not of interest, it was important to be able to establish correlation between buckling predictions and measured buckling loads before investigating the postbuckling response.

To address failure, the maximum stress criterion was used, this criterion being used because it is easy to understand and apply, and basic data are available. The stresses considered important in each layer were the fiber-direction compressive and tensile stress, σ_1 , the stress transverse to the fiber direction and in the plane of the layer, σ_2 , the shear stress in the plane of the layer, τ_{12} , and the two interlaminar shear stresses, τ_{13} and τ_{23} . Interlaminar tensile stresses were not considered important. For the $(\pm 45/0/90)_2S$, $(\pm 45/0_2)_2S$, $(\pm 45/0_6)_S$ laminates the modes considered critical were tensile or compression failure in the fiber direction (σ_1), and interlaminar shear failure (τ_{13} or τ_{13}). For the $(\pm 45)_4S$ laminate, since there were no fibers in the loading direction, failure due to τ_{12} was also considered critical. There was no progressive failure theory applied. When one of the above stresses reached critical levels, failure was assumed to have occurred.

The elastic and strength properties for the material are given in Table 1. These properties were taken from ref. 5 and 6.

4. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND CORRELATION WITH EXPERIMENT

As a first comparison between experiment and prediction, Table 2 compares the numerically predicted and the experimentally measured buckling loads for the four laminates. For each laminate two replicate plates were tested and thus the numbers in Table 2 represent averages of the two tests. As can be seen, the correlation between predicted and measured buckling loads is good, the experiment being somewhat softer in all cases.

Though considerable postbuckling experimental data were gathered and considerable numerical results calculated, only applied load vs. shortening data will be discussed here. This response is quite indicative of what is happening to the plate as regards load carrying capacity in the postbuckling range. Figure 2 provides a comparison of load vs. shorten response and failure predictions for the four laminates. Referring the legend for fig. 2, on each subfigure in fig. 2 are the following: 1 - The numerically predicted load vs. shortening relation for the laminate responding in the one halfwave configuration; 2 - The numerically predicted load vs. shortening relation for the laminate responding in the two halfwave configuration; 3 - The experimentally measured load vs. shortening relation for the first of the two replicate laminates; and, 4 - The experimentally measured load vs. shortening relation for the second of the two replicate laminates. In the figures the load is normalized by the cross-sectional area of the laminates, A , and its modulus in the loading direction, E . The shortening is normalized by the overall length of the laminate, 'a' in fig. 1. To be discussed in some detail will be the load vs. shortening response for the $(\pm 45/0/90)_2S$ laminate. The load vs. shortening relations for the other three laminates will not be discussed in as much detail. Only those points that distinguish the response of the other three laminates from that of the $(\pm 45/0/90)_2S$ laminate will be highlighted.

Referring to fig. 2a and the line representing numerical prediction for the response in the one half-wave configuration (line with long portion and two short dashes), it is seen that as the $(\pm 45/0/90)_2S$ laminate is loaded, the shortening increases in a linear fashion until buckling load is reached. At buckling the slope of the load vs. shortening relation decreases. At a value of P/EA of just greater than 0.00175, a inplane shear failure (τ_{12}) is predicted to occur in one of the layers. At a slightly higher load a transverse failure (σ_2 tension) is predicted. These two failures are not considered serious for this laminate. At a load level of 0.00256 fiber direction compression failure is predicted. This is con-

sidered to be the failure load of the plate in the one halfwave configuration. The location of failure is predicted to be the net-section hole edge. Turning to the numerical prediction for the response in the two halfwave configuration (line with long portion and one short dash), it is seen that the load vs. shortening relation follows roughly the same path as the numerically-predicted one halfwave configuration relation. At a load level of about 0.00175, transverse failure is predicted to occur in one of the layers. As the load is increased to just under 0.00250, transverse tensile and fiber compression failure are predicted. The predicted location of the fiber compression failure is along the simple support at the net section. Interlaminar failure was never an issue, the predicted level of interlaminar shear stress being low relative to the failure level, even in the two halfwave configuration. Since the plate may respond with the two halfwave configuration, and since the fiber-direction failure load for that configuration is lower than for the one halfwave configuration, the predicted failure load is taken to be 0.00244, the load that produces fiber compression failure in the two halfwave configuration.

Turning to the experimentally measured load vs. shortening relations which represent the two replicate plates (the solid and the dashed lines), it is seen that the measured relations are somewhat softer than the numerically predicted relations. Not seen in fig. 2a is the fact that upon initial loading, both laminates responded with one halfwave in the loading direction. At a load of about 0.00150, both laminates experienced a sudden change of configuration, the load level being labeled 'cc' in the figure and the configuration changing from one to two halfwaves in the loading direction. With continued loading, plate 1 failed at a level of 0.00234 and plate 2 failed at a level of 0.00271. The average of these two failure loads is 0.00253 and both plates failed along the simple support at the net section, as predicted for the two halfwave configuration. This average failure load is quite close to the predicted level of 0.00244 which corresponds to the two halfwave configuration.

The description for the subfigure the $(\pm 45/0_2)_{2S}$ laminate, fig. 2b, is quite similar. The predicted fiber compression failure load did not depend strongly on whether the plate responded with one or with two halfwaves. Though in the experiments the sudden configuration changes of the two plates were not quite at the same load levels, the measured failure loads for the two plates were practically identical, 0.00199 and 0.00201. Both plates failed along the simple supports at the net section, the predicted location for the two halfwave configuration. Table 2 compares predicted with measured failure load levels.

The $(\pm 45/0_6)_S$ laminate was predicted to experience transverse failure, shear failure, then fiber direction compression failure. Interlaminar shear failure was not predicted to be an issue. In the experiments these plates did not experience a configuration change, thus only the one halfwave prediction is shown in the fig. 2c. Fiber direction compression failure was predicted to occur in the one halfwave configuration at a load of 0.00163, the failure was predicted to occur along the simply supported edge. As can be seen, in the experiments the plates failed at levels of 0.00143 and 0.00162, the average level being 0.00154, a good comparison with the predicted level of 0.00163. Interestingly, this good comparison is quite misleading. In the experiments both replicate plates actually failed at the simple supports due to interlaminar shear, in particular τ_{yz} , which in the principal material system translates to τ_{23} for the 0° layers. Though these stresses were predicted to be high, they did not exceed the value of $S_{23} = 55$ MPa given in Table 1. It is entirely possible that with the 12 clustered 0° layers, the in situ interlaminar shear strength was much lower than 55 MPa. Using the average failure load of 0.00153, the in situ value of S_{23} for the clustered 0° layers was predicted to be 14 MPa.

Finally, the $(\pm 45)_4S$ laminate responded quite differently than predictions. First, in the one halfwave configuration significant inplane shear failure was predicted at a load level of about 0.00180, all 16 layers being predicted to fail. In the two halfwave configuration, the same type of failure was predicted to occur at a load of 0.00260. Both failures were predicted to be at the hole edge. This all-encompassing inplane shear failure was considered to be failure of the laminate, any ensuing predic-

tion of failure being meaningless. In the experiments, the plates responded by deforming in the one halfwave configuration to a load level of about 0.00300, considerably beyond the predicted level of 0.00180 when all 16 layers were predicted to fail. With loading beyond 0.00300, the plates slowly began to change to the two halfwave configuration. Accompanying the configuration change were much larger deformations than had accompanied any of the other plates. At a load level of about 0.00350, the plates failed in what looked like an inplane shear mode. This failure was not sudden, rather it was progressive, as plate deformations increased excessively. The failure occurred midway along lines connecting the center of the hole to the corners of the plates. Both replicate plates showed practically identical behavior. It is hypothesized that nonlinear stress-strain behavior of the inplane shear response of the material was responsible for the observed results. Since the analysis was linear elastic, no such behavior could be predicted.

5. CONCLUSIONS

It appears that failure of the more conventional $(\pm 45/0/90)_2S$ and $(\pm 45/0_2)_2S$ plates can be accurately predicted, if the configuration of the deformation is known. Both the location and the load level observed in the experiments correlated well with the predictions. Lacking is the ability to predict whether the one halfwave or the two halfwave configuration will dominate at failure. The attempt to predict failure in the other two laminates was not as successful. Clustering effects in the $(\pm 45/0_6)_S$ laminate and nonlinear material effects in the $(\pm 45)_4S$ tended to dominate the response of those laminates. The former issue can be addressed by using interlaminar shear strengths representative of the clustered laminate, while the latter issue can be addressed by including material nonlinearities in the analysis.

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7. REFERENCES

- 1 - Noor, A.K. Starnes, J.H. Jr., and Waters, W. A., Jr., "Numerical and Experimental Simulations of the Postbuckling Response of Laminated Anisotropic Panels," AIAA paper no. 90-0964CP, Proceedings of 31st AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AMS Structures, Structural Dynamics, and Materials Conference, 1990,
- 2 - Nemeth, M.P., "Importance of Anisotropy on Buckling of Compression Loaded Symmetric Composite Plates," AIAA J., vol. 24, Nov. 1986, pp. 1831 - 1835.
- 3 - Chaudhuri, R. A. and Siede, P. "An Approximate Semi-Analytical Method for Prediction of Interlaminar Shear Stresses in an Arbitrarily Laminated thick Plate," Computers and Structures, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 627-636, 1987.
- 4 - Lee, H.H. and Hyer, M.W., "Geometrically Nonlinear Cylindrical Bending of Laminates," Proceedings of the 6th Japan-US Conference on Composite Materials, Technomic Publishers, Inc., Lancaster, PA, pp. 115 - 124, 1992.
- 5 - Nemeth, M.P., "Buckling Behavior of Compression Loaded Symmetrically Laminated Angle-Ply Plates with Holes," AIAA J., vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 330-336, 1988.

6 - Burns, S.W., Herakovich, C.T., and Williams, J.G., "Compressive Failure of Notched Angle-Ply CompositeLamiantes: Three Dimensional Finite Element Analysis and Experiment," Virginia Tech Center for Composite Materials and Structures, CCMS-85-11, 1985.

Table 1: Material Properties

Elastic Properties	Strength Properties (Ksi)
$E_1 = 128 \text{ GPa}$ $E_2 = 11.0 \text{ GPa}$ $G_{12} = 5.74 \text{ GPa}$ $G_{23} = 2.29 \text{ GPa}$ $\nu_{12} = 0.35$	$X_t = 1.38 \text{ GPa}; X_c = -1.38 \text{ GPa}$ $Y_t = 48.3 \text{ MPa}; Y_c = -241 \text{ MPa}$ $S_{12} = S_{13} = 64.8 \text{ MPa}$ $S_{23} = 55.0 \text{ MPa}$

Table 2: Buckling and Failure Loads, P/EA¹

Laminate	E GPa	Buckling			Failure		
		Numerical	Experimental	Difference	Numerical	Experimental	Difference
$(\pm 45/0/90)_2S$	50.9	0.000411	0.000370	-10%	0.00244	0.00253	+4%
$(\pm 45/0_2)_2S$	74.5	0.000321	0.000305	-5%	0.00206	0.00200	-3%
$(\pm 45/0_6)_S$	101	0.000245	0.000234	-4%	0.00156	0.00154 ²	-6%
$(\pm 45)_4S$	19.8	0.000980	0.000880	-10%	0.00485	0.00359 ³	-26%

1 - $A = 2.16 \times 279\text{mm}^2$

2 - interlaminar shear failure at simple supported edge not predicted.

3 - poor correlation due to material nonlinearity.

Fig. 1 - Problem Definition.

Experimental end shortening — - - -	Experimental failure -	Predicted end shortening One half-wave - · - · - Two half-wave - - - -	Predicted failure	
	cc indicates configuration change.		One half-wave ■ Trans. Failure ▲ Shear failure ● Fiber failure	Two half-wave □ Trans. Failure △ Shear failure ○ Fiber failure

a. $[\pm 45/0/90]_{2s}$

b. $[\pm 45/0]_{2s}$

c. $[\pm 45/0]_6s$

d. $[\pm 45]_{4s}$

Fig. 2 - Comparison of Load vs. Shortening Relations and Failures, Experimental and Predicted.